

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

LOVELY R. TINGUHA, DBA

Assistant Professor I

Negros Oriental State University

lovely.tinguha@norsu.edu.ph

“SA ERE”

You said to wait...
But how long?

It's been eons now
My hearts not strong

I may fall
I may play

Either way
It's still you I long?

How long?
How long?!

Will I stay in the air
Toss here and there?

Not knowing
You're not showing